

Modelling and Control of Differential Drive Wheeled Mobile Vehicle

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Abstract— This research paper is presented effective algorithm for modelling and control of differential drive ground vehicle. Black-Box type modelling is performed to generate dynamic transfer functions for the two DC motors of mobile robot through System Identification in Matlab without the need to know mechanical concept of a DC motor. Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers are designed for speed and position control of the vehicle to maintain the desired performance for reducing inaccuracies of the system because of systematic error such as modelling faults. Generalized forward kinematic of differential drive mobile robot is used to transform desired position at lateral and longitudinal motion of the vehicle. Performance of the controllers are analysed in point to point motion task and simulation results are verified in Matlab Simulink.

Keywords— Differential drive, Black-box modelling, PID controller, Speed control, Position control

I. INTRODUCTION

The developments of unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) have been increasing due to their possible use in different environments. Ground mobile robots can be separated into wheeled, legged, and tracked mobile robots. Among them, differential wheeled type is most used structure because of the consequence of low energy consumptions, and less complexity of mathematical model.

The main objective of this research is intended to the position and speed control of the two-wheel differential drive mobile robot using the Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controllers. The system of the research is separated into two levels of control structure which are speed control at low level, and position control at high level. A mobile robot may face systematic error and non-systematic error. The systematic error will be formed because of the inaccuracies at the system of robot such as modelling error. Non-systematic error will be caused due to external disturbance such as environment conditions. This system is designed to reduce the systematic error, neglecting non-linear disturbance. For this reason, linear control scheme is sufficient for the system, so, PID control method is developed in control task of this research.

A. Background Research

A variety of background research has been proposed about modelling and control for differential drive mobile vehicle. Research [1] provides detail experiments of data collection in system modelling and mathematical form of system identification for UGV system. Reference paper [2] presents black-box modelling through system identification in Matlab intended for electrical engineers without the knowledge on mechanical concepts. Paper [3] presents the development of speed control for non-autonomous mobile vehicle for driving under difficult environment condition of

surveillance aim at DORIS project. Reference [4] describes modelling, speed control, lateral and longitudinal motion control of differential drive UGV system for leader-follower formation system.

B. Proposed System

The system of the research is described in Fig. 1. The robot used in this study consists of three wheels. One wheel is free, and others are DC gear motor drive. An optical encoder is fixed at each wheel of the robot to sense speed of the wheel. In this research, System Identification toolbox in Matlab is supported for the black-box modelling of the motors at left and right sides of the robot. This type of modelling does not need to measure physical parameters of the system. It needs only experimental data (Input and Output data) in time.

Figure 1. Control block of the system.

At the inner loop control scheme, the two dc motors have different dynamic equations according to the system identification. A PID controller for each motor are used to achieve the desired performance at speed of the motors. The outer loop, position control contains longitudinal and lateral PID controllers to perform desired criterions at distance travels and orientation of the mobile robot. Generalized forward kinematic is transformed from the speed of two DC motor (V_1 and V_r) controlled differential-drive wheels and the parameters of robot frame to generate distance and orientation angle that robot travels. These are required for feedback of the outer loop.

C. Organization

This paper presents modelling and control for ground mobile robot. It is organized as follows. Section II presents system architecture and main concepts that are required essential information to design this system. Section III describes system modelling in System Identification. Section IV presents controller designs for this research with simulation results. Finally, Section V discusses the conclusions and future works.

II. MOBILE ROBOT

The two 12V Tetrax dc motors are implemented for left and right sides of the robot in which the specifications of the gear ratio of 2:1 and output speed of 152 RPM. The two motors of the robot are connected with L298 Dual H-Bridge motor driver which allows speed and direction of two DC motors. It can drive DC motors that have voltages between 5 and 35V, with a peak current up to 2A. 8-bit PWM (Pulse-Width-Modulation) signal is applied to the motor driver to adjust the speed of the two DC motors.

Figure 2. Mobile Robot of the system.

Arduino Uno is implemented to drive the motors by applying PWM signal to the motor driver and to read sensors (encoders) data for the feedback loop. It is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328P. The software used for this controller is Arduino Software (IDE). In this research, the two quadrature optical encoders are implemented in the differential drive robot to measure the wheel speed. The encoder counts the digital pulses by Arduino Uno microcontroller board which is used to determine the wheel displacement. And then, this count value is directly converted to the rate of displacement in radian per second. The encoders used in this research have the specifications of 5V supply voltage, 100 CPR (Count per Revolution), and 400 PPR (Pulse per Revolution).

In this research, System Identification toolbox in Matlab is supported for the black-box modelling to estimate dynamic transfer functions of the two DC motor and also Simulink is the main tool in designing PID controllers for speed and position control of the mobile robot.

III. SYSTEM MODELLING

In this system, input and output data logging of the DC motors by an experiment of moving the mobile robot in forward and backward directions and estimate dynamic model from this data with the help of System Identification in Matlab. Although black box modelling is fast running and less computational power, this type of model is lack of flexibility.

If the model needs to be changed to describe something physically only slightly different, it can mean a lot of work to determine any new rules or bulk parameters. A black box model is not appropriate for any form of sensitivity analysis. The control system of this research does not study about non-systematic disturbance. For this reason black box modelling is compatible.

The black-box modelling is performed to estimate plant model of DC motors of the vehicle using experimental input and output data at appropriate time interval. The flowchart in Fig. 3 describes the procedure of modelling in system identification.

Figure 3. Procedure of modelling in system identification.

Data acquisition is the collecting of input and output data to find the dynamic models for left and right sides of the robot. To obtain best model of vehicle transfer function, data acquisition of the experimental data must be accurate so that the data must catch appropriate sampling interval, which is important factor in system identification. In this research, sampling time (T_s) of 0.1 second is used during data acquisition. This sampling frequency is high enough for UGV dynamic. The smaller sampling time creates more accurate system modelling but limitation must be noticed. The sampling frequency must not be less than the twice of system dynamic frequency ($F_s \geq 2F_{max}$). Moreover, this experimental data must be changed due to the different environment such as rough or smooth floor and also at the condition of low power battery. Data acquisition of this research is in the smooth floor. The input data to the two dc motors is 8-bit PWM values and the output data is the speed measurement from the encoder. Pulses measured from the encoders are counted and converted to the rad/s by Eq. 1.

$$\text{Velocity, } \omega \text{ (rad/s)} = \frac{\frac{\text{Encoder Pulses}}{\text{revolution}} \times \frac{60 \text{ sec}}{\text{min}}}{\text{Fixed time interval (sec)}} \times \frac{2\pi}{60} \quad (1)$$

After the data acquisition, input and output data for each motors are imported to system identification toolbox. Fig. 4 shows the input and output data plots of the left and right sides.

Figure 4. Input and output data logging (a) left motor (b) right motor

The next step is to generate transfer functions in different orders. Among them, second order with no zero and two poles was chosen for both left and right motors with best fits of 77.54% and 80.17% respectively shown in Fig. 5.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Transfer function estimation in system identification toolbox (a) left motor (b) right motor

After generating transfer functions, model validation was performed, which is the process of comparing the output of simulated transfer function and real system measured data output. In this system, model validation is performed different input and output data to the system identification toolbox again and compared with the simulated output of transfer function. After validation, the second order with no zero and two poles structure is the most convenient for both sides with the best fit of 73.44% and 79.42% shown in Fig. 6.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. Validation (a) left motor (b) right motor.

Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 are the chosen transfer functions of left and right sides of vehicle.

$$\frac{\omega}{V} = \frac{2.148}{s^2 + 31.77s + 156.8} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\omega}{V} = \frac{2.296}{s^2 + 41.45s + 170.8} \quad (3)$$

According to the system step response of the motors, both motors achieve one half of the desired output, that is, at the input of 1 rad/s, the output is near 0.45 rad/s, and also rise time. To compensate this problem, PID controller is developed for each motor to compensate desired performance in the minimum time possible and the minimum overshoot.

IV. CONTROLLER DESIGNS AND SIMULATION

For the control structure of this research describes in Fig. 1, PID controllers for inner loop; speed control and outer loop; position control for the mobile vehicle is described in this section.

A. PID Controller for Speed Control

The dynamic transfer functions of the two DC motors shown in Eq. 3 and Eq. 4 are different so a PID controller must be developed for each left and right sided motors. PID controllers are designed in Matlab Simulink, and the performance of different controller P (Proportional), PI (Proportional-Integral), and PID (Proportional-Integral-Differential) for both manual and auto tuning are analyzed. The control block diagram of speed control for two sided motor is shown in the following figure, Fig. 7. Desired performance specifications is regarded as the settling time

is less than 0.3 second, rise time is less than 0.2 second, and percent overshoot is less than 2% for the speed control.

Figure 7. Control Block of Speed Control.

In PID controller design, firstly, manual Proportional (P) controller was tried by using the Table. 2. Increasing proportional gain (K_p) has the effect of reducing rise time. The open loop model output is smaller than desired speed as discussed previous article. So the system is needed to increase K_p . But the greater the K_p , the higher the maximum overshoot. It is not convenient the desired Percent Overshoot criterion of less than 2%.

TABLE I. EFFECTS OF PARAMETERS IN PID CONTROLLER

Parameter	Rise Time (T_r)	Maximum Overshoot (M_p)	Settling Time (T_s)	Steady State Error (E_{ss})
K_p	Decrease	Increase	Small Change	Decrease
K_i	Decrease	Increase	Increase	Eliminate
K_d	Minor Change	Decrease	Decrease	No effect

Then, Proportional-Integral Controller (PI) was tried and also high percent overshoot at high value of K_i . So, K_i decreases to reduce percent overshoot, but settling time increases again. To reduce settling time, the system is needed to combine with differential gain K_d . So, among P, PI, and PID controllers, Proportional -Integral-Differential controller (PID) is the best performance for this system.

PID auto tuning result with Matlab PID tuner application and best results of PID manual tuning for left and right motors are shown in Fig. 8 (a) and (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Closed loop step response with different controllers (a) left motor (b) right motor.

The comparisons of the closed loop response's characteristics with different controllers for the left motor are shown in Table. 2.

TABLE II. EFFECTS OF PARAMETERS IN PID CONTROLLER

Controller	K_p	K_i	K_d	Rise Time (sec)	Settling Time (sec)	Maximum Percent Overshoot (%)	Peak Time (sec)	Steady State Error
PID (manual)	6	30	0.09	0.1333	0.2145	0	0.6434	0
PID (auto)	4.341	35.334	0.0884	0.1444	0.5099	7.5080	0.3091	0
P (Manual)	700	0	0	0.005	0.2452	79.5953	0.0143	0
PI (Manual)	10	50	0	0.0645	0.3259	12.8588	0.1366	0

The closed loop response characteristics with different controllers of right motor are described in Table. 3.

TABLE III. EFFECTS OF PARAMETERS IN PID CONTROLLER

Controller	K_p	K_i	K_d	Rise Time (sec)	Settling Time (sec)	Maximum Percent Overshoot (%)	Peak Time (sec)	Steady State Error
PID (manual)	9.5	38.5	0.15	0.1154	0.2008	0	0.6674	0
PID (auto)	3.836	28.0175	0.0519	0.1444	0.5099	7.5080	0.3091	0
P (Manual)	500	0	0	0.0059	0.1841	71.0526	0.0164	0
PI (Manual)	10	20	0	0.0958	1.0733	0	2.3622	0

As conclusion of speed control, according to the simulations results in Fig. 8, Table. 2 and Table. 3, PID manual tuning is the best result for both motors.

B. Kinematic of Differential drive Mobile Robot

Kinematic equations of a differential drive mobile vehicle in this article support to derive the position of the robot (distance and orientation) from the left and right wheel velocity (V_l and V_r) shown in Fig. 9 in which V_r is the velocity of the right wheel, V_l is the velocity of left wheel, L is the distance between the center of the wheels, θ is the directional angle of the robot with respect to the reference coordinate system and r is the radius of the wheel.

Figure 9. Parameters of differential drive mobile robot

The velocity for left wheel (V_l) and right wheel (V_r) and are sent to the kinematic equations to calculate the linear (V) and angular velocities (ω or θ') of the robot. By integrating these velocities the desired distance (d) and orientation angle (θ) are achieved and this values are the feedback to the position controllers for lateral and longitudinal motion.

Kinematics is the branch of classical mechanics which describes the motion of a point (object's center) without consideration to the mass of the objects or the forces that may have caused the motion. The kinematic equations are used to transform the motion from polar coordinates (r, θ) to the rectangular coordinate (x, y) system. As mentioned earlier, the inputs required for the motion of a mobile robot are the linear velocity (V) and the orientation (θ). The rate of change of position of robot in x-direction is \dot{x} and that in y-direction is \dot{y} are given by

$$\dot{x} = V \cos(\theta) \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{y} = V \sin(\theta) \quad (5)$$

And the angular velocity (ω) and linear velocity (V) of the robot are given by

$$\theta' = \omega = \frac{V_l - V_r}{L} \quad (6)$$

$$V = \frac{V_r + V_l}{2} \quad (7)$$

By substituting linear velocity (V) in Eq.4 and Eq. 5,

$$\dot{x} = \frac{V_r + V_l}{2} \cos(\theta) \quad (8)$$

$$\dot{y} = \frac{V_r + V_l}{2} \sin(\theta) \quad (9)$$

The velocity V of the robot in a fixed reference coordinate system is therefore given by

$$V = \sqrt{\dot{x}^2 + \dot{y}^2} \quad (10)$$

By substituting Eq. 8 and Eq. 9 in Eq. 10,

$$V = \sqrt{\left(\frac{V_r + V_l}{2} \cos(\theta)\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_r + V_l}{2} \sin(\theta)\right)^2} \quad (11)$$

The individual velocities, V_r and V_l ,

$$V_l = \left(V + \frac{L}{2} \omega\right) \quad (12)$$

$$V_r = \left(V - \frac{L}{2} \omega\right) \quad (13)$$

According to the kinematic equations, the value of the linear velocity (V) and angular velocity (ω) in Eq. 6 and Eq. 7 is integrated to form the distance (d) and orientation angle (θ) which are used as the feedback for position controllers.

C. Lateral PID Controller

Lateral PID controller compensates the mobile robot to travel to reach set-point angle (θ) at desired performance. Reference of lateral PID controller is orientation angle (θ) and the control effort of the lateral controller is only speed of right motor because the robot is changed its orientation by controlling the speed of right motor. To tune lateral PID controller, velocity of the mobile robot is set as constant. Control block of lateral PID controller is shown in Fig. 10.

According to the block diagram in Fig. 10, the angle (θ) must be derived from the speed of the left and right motor V_r and V_l with respect to the kinematic equations of

the differential drive mobile robot. By Eq. 6, angular velocity is $\theta' = \omega = \frac{V_l - V_r}{36.6}$.

Figure 10. Block diagram of lateral PID controller

In which equation, by the frame structure of the robot used in this research, distance between left and right wheels, $L = 36.6$ cm. Then, angle (θ) is calculated by integrating angular velocity in time in which the orientation angle is the unit of radian. The output angle is converted from radian to degree ($1^\circ = 2\pi/360 \cong 0.01745$ radian). Fig. 11 shows the step response of Lateral PID controller.

Figure 11. Step response of lateral PID controller

By PID tuning for lateral PID controller, P controller is the best response with the performance in settling time of 0.0576 second, rise time of 0.102 second, and 0% overshoot.

D. Longitudinal PID Controller

Longitudinal PID controller is designed to compensate the linear velocity (V) to move the robot to the desired distance. The reference of the longitudinal controller is the desired distance (d) and the control effort is the velocity of the mobile robot. Control block of longitudinal PID controller is shown in Fig. 12.

Figure 12. Block Diagram of longitudinal PID controller

To tune longitudinal PID controller, the set-point orientation angle is fixed at '0' degree. According to the block diagram in Fig. 12, output distance (d) is derived from the left and right wheels' velocities (V_l and V_r) by using the kinematic equations. By Eq. 7, the linear velocity is the average of the summation of the left and right wheels' velocities ($V = (V_l + V_r)/2$ rad/s). The constant multiple of the radius of the wheel used in the robot and linear velocity in rad/s is formed the linear velocity of the robot in cm/s (V (cm/s) = r (cm) \times V

(rad/s)). The radius (r) of the wheel used in the mobile robot in this research is 4.8cm. The distance travel of the robot is the integrating of the linear velocity of the robot in time. Fig. 13 describes step response of longitudinal PID controller.

Figure 13. Step Response of longitudinal PID controller

By tuning longitudinal PID controller, PD controller at $K_p= 15.5786$, $K_d=1.018$ is the best response with the sufficient performance in rise time of 0.112 second, settling time of 0.28 second and 0.0353% overshoot.

E. Point to Point Motion of Mobile Robot

After integrating lateral and longitudinal controllers, performance simulation of position control in point to point motion of the mobile robot is described in this article.

Figure 14. Point to Point Coordinate from Distance and Orientation.

The desired distance and angle from the desired position (x, y) is calculated by the point to point equations from Eq. 13 to Eq. 16.

$$d = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2} \quad (13)$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{(y_2 - y_1)}{(x_2 - x_1)} \quad (14)$$

$$x = x_0 + d \cos(\theta) \quad (15)$$

$$y = y_0 + d \sin(\theta) \quad (16)$$

Fig. 15 shows simulation result position control in point to point motion task.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 15. Simulation of Position Control (a) Change in Distance (b) Change in Angle (c) Point to Point Tracking

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

This research paper proposed black-box modelling, speed and position control of differential drive mobile ground vehicle. In this paper, linearized black-box modelling using system identification and PID controller designs to compensate desired performance at speed and position are also described.

In modelling, since input-output data is collected by driving the robot on the smooth floor, transfer functions will be fault at different environments and also non-linear disturbances will be occurred. For this reason, the studies on sensitivities based on non-systematic error sources using non-linear adaptive control methods should be a future research. Most common mobile robot system is based on the differential drive model in which two powered wheels used for both driving and changing direction as the same as this system. Omnidirectional mobile robot system in which both driving and changing are performed by the front steering is more accurate than this system. So, front steering mobile robot system should be a future research.

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